

CONTEMPORARY TEACHING OF LISTENING SKILLS METHODS

Vafayeva Malika Vafoyevna

Shavat district, Khorezm region

14th general secondary school

English teacher

Annotation: The article talks about teaching listening skills using modern methods. Also given below is one of the easy ways to improve your listening comprehension skills.

Keywords: Audio segments, Group activities, Video segments, Interpersonal activities.

Аннотация: В статье говорится об обучении навыкам аудирования с использованием современных методик. Также ниже приведен один из простых способов улучшить свои навыки восприятия на слух.

Ключевые слова: аудиосегменты, групповые действия, видеосегменты, межличностные действия.

Among the four skills that are important in learning any language, listening comprehension is central. In the field of language teaching and learning, speaking and writing a language is usually considered as the primary language use factor. Listening and reading skills come second. One reason for this may be that it is

somewhat difficult to master listening skills. But after the spread of IT technology, listening comprehension has become much easier to pass through different materials in language classes. In addition, it should be noted that most of the students' class time began to be devoted to listening. We have come to believe in the importance of listening more often. In the natural order of learning any language, listening began to take the leading place. Everyone began to be convinced that mastering only one skill alone would not produce anything. Teachers began to pay more attention to teaching their students not only speaking fluency, but also listening comprehension. Perfect acquisition and use of a new language requires formation of existing knowledge and learning all the necessary information based on language receptive skills, especially listening and reading skills. In this regard, a language learning program has been created for the convenience of learners. According to the structure of this program, it should not contain any input tests, result or output anything. Listening training is very relevant today, because speech communication is impossible without listening. The concept of listening includes the process of perceiving and understanding spoken speech. Listening is definitely an important aspect in learning English. Modern effective methods of teaching listening skills include everything from interactive exercises to multimedia resources. Listening is considered to be the most learned skill. Because a little more focus on learning is enhanced through simple and fun activities and ultimately leads to better results. In this case, it doesn't matter whether you work with small or large groups of students, as long as you use one of the following methods to develop yourself.

Unique ways to teach students to listen well:

Interpersonal activity

Interpersonal activities are one of the most effective ways to develop strong listening skills in students. We can add the following to this method:

1. Role playing
2. Mock interviews
3. Interpersonal dialogues
4. Storytelling and more

In this, students are divided into small groups of two or three, and they are asked questions according to the style.

For example, you can tell a student to interview for a job at a company or for an article in a newspaper. And storytelling activities can greatly develop students by giving them opportunities to ask questions.

Group activity

Large group activities also help students develop listening comprehension through interaction. A simple group activity is also a good way to teach students listening skills. For the first activity, students will be divided into groups of five or more and you should ask them to study one interest or at least two other hobbies. It is necessary to ask clarifying questions to the students. During the activity and you can let them take notes because it is useful. The second part of the activity is to allow students to sit in large groups.

For example, let them communicate the name of the group member they encountered and their hobbies. Both of these activities lead to effective listening growth.

Audio segments

You can also teach students listening skills through audio segments such as:

1. radio programs
2. educational lectures
3. with online podcasts and other audio messages.

Interactive listening programs should be used with students in and after the classroom. It is necessary to create conditions for them to perform the exercise independently. First of all, prepare the students to listen by giving instructions and imagining whatever you want to teach. It is up to each teacher to choose shorter or longer audio segments and more difficult or easier material for these types of exercises. Teachers can use interesting messages to engage students. You can get them from radio or TV. It is also appropriate to use the computer to convey messages to them. Students do not need to understand all the words, but they must listen carefully to the messages and know what the message is about.

Video segments

Another very useful resource for teaching listening skills is video segments that:

1. brief sketches
2. documentaries

3. dramatic or comedic material

4. news programs

5. may have interview segments. As with the audio segment, the teacher can choose the part and length of the audio based on the level of their students, which they can do the same for the video segment. One of the main conditions of this method is to watch it without any sound and discuss it together with the student. It improves students' listening and thinking skills. Movies and TV shows. Movies are one of the art forms. Language learners are recommended to watch TV to increase their vocabulary and deepen their knowledge. Movies are one of the most used teaching methods, because in movies a wide range of vocabulary can be discovered.

In conclusion, it should be said that this article has provided several methods and guidelines for developing listening comprehension skills. No matter which method you use to teach listening, there are a few basic guidelines to keep in mind. First, do not expect great results from the students at first, because even the most capable listener will never remember the message completely and clearly from the initial exercises. Secondly, it is very important to create questions for students not only clearly, but at the level of their abilities, so as not to make mistakes. Third, to help students find their own direction and style. If these rules are followed, the students will definitely acquire better listening comprehension, because no matter what the method is, they will definitely improve their listening comprehension skills.

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